

Requirement Specification

for a VR-Based Safety Training System

With a use case in Battery Production

Authors

Marianne Garabetian & Nazmiyeh Sadiyeh

Chalmers University of Technology

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Definitions and Acronyms

BCG	Battery Centre Gothenburg – The industrial and educational partner for this case study on battery safety training.
DR	Data Requirement – A requirement related to data storage, tracking, export, anonymization, and compliance (e.g., GDPR).
FR	Functional Requirement – A requirement that defines what the system must do, including features, actions, and behaviors triggered by users or events.
FPS	Frames Per Second – A performance measure indicating how smoothly graphics are rendered; higher FPS ensures less motion sickness and better immersion.
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation – European law governing the collection, storage, and processing of personal data.
HCI	Human-Computer Interaction – The study and design of interfaces and interactions between humans and digital systems.
NFR	Non-Functional Requirement – Requirements describing system quality attributes such as performance, usability, or scalability.
OpenXR	Open Extended Reality – An open standard API that supports cross-platform VR/AR development.
PII	Personally Identifiable Information – Data that can be used to identify an individual, such as names, emails, or user IDs.
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment – Safety gear used to minimize exposure to workplace hazards.
SR	System Requirement – A requirement that defines the technical and architectural constraints of the system, such as hardware specs, platform support, or installation format.
SUS	System Usability Scale – A standard 10-item questionnaire used to assess usability.
UCD	User-Centered Design – A framework that places users’ needs and feedback at the center of design and development.
Unity	Unity Game Engine – A platform for developing 3D, 2D, AR, and VR applications.
UR	User Requirement – A requirement based on the user’s needs, comfort, expectations, and preferences during training.
VR	Virtual Reality – An immersive simulation that users interact with via head-mounted displays and motion controllers.

- XR** Extended Reality – A collective term for immersive technologies, including VR, Augmented Reality (AR) and Mixed Reality (MR).
- XR2** Qualcomm XR2 Chipset – A high-performance processor used in modern standalone VR headsets.

1. Introduction

Workplace safety is an important concern in many high-risk industrial settings, particularly where hazardous materials, complex equipment, or fast-paced environments are involved. Traditional safety training methods, such as lectures, videos, or manuals, often struggle to maintain engagement and fail to provide hands-on experience. These limitations can lead to poor knowledge retention and an increased risk of accidents. There is a need for training systems that simulate realistic, high-risk situations where users can safely practice decision-making and safety-critical tasks.

1.1. Purpose, Goals and Scope

The purpose of this document is to define requirements for a general Virtual Reality (VR) safety training system. This can be adapted to different industrial training contexts. Additionally, this document provides specific requirements for battery safety training, to address the unique requirements and challenges associated with battery manufacturing safety procedures. All requirement categories are applicable both to general VR safety training systems and to the specific case of battery safety training. The system is mainly focused on usability, engagement, and knowledge retention. An important part of this is ensuring that the simulated hazards feel realistic, allowing users to practice handling them in a safe but realistic environment. The use case will focus on VR training in battery manufacturing, where improper handling can lead to severe safety hazards, including electrical shocks, chemical leaks, and fire hazards.

This requirement specification is structured based on the framework from Lauesen’s “Software Requirements: Styles and Techniques” [1] and follows the IEEE 830-1998 Software Requirements Specification Standard [2]. The IEEE 830-1998 standard defines the recommended structure and content for software requirement specifications, aiming to improve clarity, completeness, and consistency.

The goal of this requirements specification is to provide a structured and reusable framework for designing and developing VR safety training systems across various industries. The requirement specification is intended to work as both a design guide and an assessment tool for developing VR-based safety training systems. In practice, it provides a checklist for developers and trainers to ensure that essential features for functionality, usability, and safety are included. The document also facilitates communication between stakeholders by making goals, constraints, and expectations explicit. It ensures that usability, training effectiveness, and real-world safety relevance are central to the design process.

In this document, the term *application* refers specifically to the VR training software developed in Unity, including user interfaces, scenario logic, feedback mechanisms, and data handling. The term *system* is used when referring to the complete training environment, including both the application and the VR hardware setup (e.g., headset, tracking and casting capabilities). This distinction is made to improve clarity and ensure accurate allocation of functional and technical responsibilities throughout the specification.

1.2. Intended Audience

The intended audience are the stakeholders involved in the development, deployment, and evaluation of VR-based safety training systems. Primary audiences include VR developers who will implement the technical aspects of the system, safety trainers and industrial educators responsible for content delivery and learner support, and UX designers focused on creating intuitive and accessible user experiences. Additionally, the specification may be of interest to researchers in human-computer interaction (HCI) and VR training, who are exploring the effectiveness and usability of immersive learning environments.

1.3. Rationale and Criteria for Requirement Prioritization

The prioritization of requirements into high, medium, and low categories was determined based on their impact on system safety, core functionality, and user experience. High-priority requirements were identified as those directly related to safety-critical tasks and essential training objectives, which are necessary for user safety. Medium-priority requirements were selected as features that improve usability, engagement, and performance but are not essential for basic operation. Low-priority requirements were classified as supportive or nice-to-have features that can be implemented in later development stages if needed. The following criteria need to be fulfilled:

- **High-priority requirements:** 100% fulfillment is mandatory.
- **Medium-priority requirements:** At least 70–80% fulfillment is recommended.
- **Low-priority requirements:** Fulfillment is desirable but not required.

Overall, achieving at least 70-80% fulfillment of the requirements indicates that the system is effective enough for industrial deployment. This threshold is based on our own interpretation of what defines a functional and practical system in real-world settings. It is combined with 100% completion of all high-priority requirements, which is based on established practices in software engineering and XR training system evaluation. Kitchenham et al. discuss the importance of defining clear success criteria and using measurable outcomes when evaluating system performance in software engineering research [3]. Setting a specific percentage target makes the evaluation process more transparent. Furthermore, the IEEE 830-1998 standard highlights how requirement prioritization ensures that critical, high-priority features are fully implemented to make a system acceptable for use [2].

1.4. Overview

Table 1 below summarizes the distribution of priorities across all 61 identified requirements.

1.5. Reference to thesis report

This requirement specification is part of a master’s thesis project titled “*Battery Safety Training in Virtual Reality - Evaluating VR as an industrial training platform for the future battery industry*”. For the full methodology, including survey questions and interview details, please see the full thesis report.

Category	Total	High	Medium	Low
General Functional Requirements (FR)	13	7	5	1
Battery Production Functional Requirements (FR-B)	8	6	2	0
Non-Functional Requirements (NFR)	12	6	4	2
System Requirements (SR)	11	8	3	0
User Requirements (UR)	11	6	4	1
Data Requirements (DR)	6	4	2	0
Total	61	37	20	4

Table 1: Summary of requirements and prioritization.

2. Stakeholders

The following stakeholder groups are involved in or affected by the system:

- **Trainees**, who are the primary users of the system.
- **Instructors and/or safety trainers**, who use the platform to guide and assess learning.
- **VR developers and designers**, responsible for implementing the system regarding the requirements.
- **Battery Centre Gothenburg (BCG)**, the industrial partner for this project, providing use case insights.
- **Researchers**, who may use the system to study VR training effectiveness, engagement, and user behavior.

3. Sources and Methods for Requirements Definition

The requirements presented in this specification are based on multiple data sources. The following sources and methods were used to define and prioritize requirements:

- **User testing and survey:** Feedback was gathered from 78 participants, including battery assembly workers at a Swedish Battery Assembly Facility and students from Higher Vocational Education (*Yrkeshögskolan*). Participants evaluated the VR training experience and provided insights into usability, engagement, and learning effectiveness.
- **Group interviews:** Semi-structured group interviews with 8 groups with 4-5 participants in each group from battery assembly workers at Volvo Torslanda. Participants were asked about their experience and to provide feedback on improvements.
- **User testing observations:** Direct observations were made during user testing sessions to identify usability challenges, unclear interactions, and difficulties with task completion.
- **Stakeholder interviews:** Input was collected through interviews with stakeholders, including the Operations Manager and a trainer at BCG.

- **Literature review:** Best practices and standards from academic sources informed system performance targets and user experience requirements.

4. Functional Requirements

This section defines the functional requirements of the VR-based safety training system. These requirements describe the core features and system behaviors necessary to support effective user interaction, immersive learning, and safe task execution. They specify what the system must do to fulfill stakeholder expectations and ensure training outcomes such as usability, knowledge retention, realism, and correct task execution. The functional requirements are divided into two categories:

- **General Functional Requirements**, which apply to a wide range of industrial safety training scenarios.
- **Battery Production–Specific Functional Requirements**, which address hazards, tools, and procedures unique to battery manufacturing environments.

The functional requirements were identified through a combination of methods. Initial insights were gathered from reviewing the existing VR training system used at BCG and observations of user testing sessions. These were further validated and expanded through stakeholder interviews, as well as feedback from user testing sessions with both students and industry participants.

4.1. General Functional Requirements

This subsection describes the main functional requirements applicable to a wide range of industrial VR safety training systems.

Req ID	Requirement	User Task	Rationale	Priority
FR-1	The application shall provide immediate visual, auditory, and/or haptic feedback for user actions.	React to system events	Reinforces learning and helps identify mistakes in real time.	High
FR-2	The application shall allow users to restart or rewind a scenario after failure.	Retry and reflect on mistakes	Supports learning from failure without consequences.	High
FR-3	The application shall track and log user actions during a scenario anonymously.	Record learning journey	Enables trainers to evaluate progress and mistakes.	High
FR-4	The application shall include a tutorial/practice stage with clear instructions on how to interact with specific objects in the system.	Practice interaction with objects	Onboard into VR. Ensure users can complete all tasks without breaking immersion.	High
FR-5	The application shall provide additional guidance when the user is stuck on a certain step/task (e.g., through a help button)	Gain understanding and resume task	Prevents user frustration and supports continued learning.	High
FR-6	The application shall provide concise audio alerts and safety instructions during high-stress or time-critical scenarios, such as "Evacuate immediately" or "Gas leak detected, put on face mask"	Understand instructions clearly and react quickly	Supports user focus and safety by delivering essential guidance without relying solely on text, especially in moments of urgency or cognitive overload	High
FR-7	The system shall support screen casting so that a trainer can observe the session and intervene when necessary.	Instructor involvement	Allows trainers to monitor user performance in real time and provide immediate feedback or assistance when required.	High
FR-8	The application shall provide information about missed steps during post-scenario feedback.	Review mistakes clearly	Improves reflection and procedural recall.	Medium

FR-9	The application shall integrate a “checklist panel” showing task progress during or in between scenarios.	Track progress	Helps users stay on task without feeling overwhelmed.	Medium
FR-10	The application shall include a final exam scenario that evaluates the user’s ability to perform tasks without assistance.	Demonstrate learning outcomes	Validates knowledge retention and procedural understanding through independent performance assessment.	High
FR-11	The application shall allow users to adjust font size, contrast, and control schemes.	Customize interface	Supports accessibility and inclusivity for users with visual or physical needs.	Low
FR-12	The system shall simulate environmental distractions (alarms, noise, time pressure) in advanced scenarios.	Maintain focus under stress	Prepares users for realistic high-pressure situations common in safety-critical environments.	High
FR-13	The application shall allow users to pause between scenarios and restart or rewind a scenario	Resume training comfortably in case of dizziness, cognitive overload, or motion sickness	Enhances comfort and accessibility by allowing users to manage breaks without losing progress.	High

4.2. Battery Production - Specific Functional Requirements

This subsection outlines functional requirements specific to safety training in battery production environments. These are in addition to the general requirements described earlier.

Req ID	Requirement	User Task	Rationale	Priority
FR-B1	The application shall simulate safety-critical scenarios including chemical spills, battery overheating, fire hazards, and electric shock.	Handle hazards	The tasks reflect real-world risks and are essential for learning.	High
FR-B2	The application shall simulate realistic consequences for incorrect actions.	Learn from errors	Engages users and improves recall of safety outcomes.	High

FR-B3	The application shall include steps of battery production relevant to safety training, such as inspection, assembly, testing, and handling procedures.	Follow safe procedures	Ensures that users experience realistic, end-to-end workflows that reinforce correct behavior at each stage of the battery production process.	High
FR-B4	The application shall allow interaction with realistic tools used in battery environments (e.g., multimeters, torque wrenches, thermal sensors).	Use realistic equipment	Reinforces tactile familiarity with industry-relevant tools.	Medium
FR-B5	The application shall include scenes simulating evacuation and/or post evacuation situations during escalating hazard such as thermal runaway.	Respond to full emergencies	Broadens scope of safety beyond just equipment handling.	High
FR-B6	The application shall simulate contamination risks and enforce proper chemical handling protocols, including hygiene and disposal procedures.	Practice chemical safety	Reinforces awareness of contamination hazards and safe handling of chemicals common in battery production environments.	High
FR-B7	The application shall enforce PPE usage when performing tasks involving high-voltage or hazardous chemicals, and shall simulate consequences of non-compliance.	Apply chemical and electrical safety protocols	Emphasizes the importance of wearing correct protective equipment when working with live components, energized systems or hazardous chemicals.	High
FR-B8	The application shall verify and confirm when a critical safety step is correctly completed (e.g., voltage measurement, polarity check).	Receive confirmation of correct action	Ensures users are performing essential steps accurately and provides immediate feedback to reinforce correct behavior.	High

5. Non-Functional Requirements

This section describes the quality standards that the VR safety training system must meet. These requirements focus on how the system should behave, not what features it provides. The non-functional requirements in this specification are primarily based on VR development best practices identified through literature review, including performance guidelines to reduce motion sickness and improve immersion.

Req ID	Requirement	User Task	Rationale	Priority
NFR-1	The system shall maintain at least 90 FPS to ensure smooth performance.	Maintain visual comfort	Prevents motion sickness and supports immersion	High
NFR-2	Feedback (visual/haptic/audio) shall be delivered within 300ms of action.	Get real-time response	Keeps interaction responsive and natural	High
NFR-3	The system should aim for a SUS score of 80 or higher in usability evaluations.	Measure usability	Targets high ease of use and satisfaction across a diverse user base, including first-time VR users	Medium
NFR-4	The application shall support English as the primary language	Accessible communication	Supports language needs for international trainees and reinforces industry-relevant language	High
NFR-5	The application shall support the local language	Accessible communication	Supports language needs for local trainees.	Low
NFR-6	No more than two instruction elements shall be visible at once.	Prevent cognitive overload	Reduces distraction and confusion.	High
NFR-7	The application shall follow industry best practices and user experience guidelines for startup responsiveness	Startup responsiveness	Improves user perception and readiness.	Medium
NFR-8	The application shall use fade-in/fade-out visual transitions between scenarios.	Maintain immersion during loading	Provides a smoother, more comfortable scene switch that reduces disorientation.	Low
NFR-9	A scenario shall be able to restart within 5 seconds after completion or failure.	Quickly retry	Encourages iteration and flow by minimizing downtime between attempts.	Medium

NFR-10	The application shall display a visual loading indicator (e.g., progress bar, spinning icon, or transition screen) between scenes	Understand loading status	Prevents confusion and discomfort by informing users when the system is loading and not frozen.	Medium
NFR-11	The application shall use asynchronous scene loading methods to prevent headset freezing during transitions	Avoid system freezes	Maintains user comfort and application stability across sessions.	High
NFR-12	The application shall avoid VR mechanics known to cause motion sickness (e.g., artificial locomotion, abrupt camera shifts)	Comfort design	Supports user well-being and minimizes VR-induced discomfort across training sessions.	High

6. System Requirements

This section describes the technical and system-level requirements for the VR safety training application. These include the development tools used, supported hardware, installation method, and the performance levels needed for the system to run smoothly. System requirements were defined based on the technical capabilities and limitations from Meta Horizon [4], as well as the Unity development environment used for building the training application.

Req ID	Requirement	User Task	Rationale	Priority
SR-1	The application shall be developed using Unity with OpenXR support.	Cross-platform compatibility	Allows deployment across various headsets.	High
SR-2	The application shall be compatible with all major standalone VR headsets that support OpenXR or equivalent standards.	Hardware deployment	Ensures flexibility across various VR devices without locking the system to specific brands.	High
SR-3	The application footprint should not exceed 2 GB on target headsets.	Efficient storage	Reduces installation friction and ensures compatibility with devices that have limited available storage.	High
SR-4	The system shall provide a calibration step (e.g setting boundaries in the room) before each session.	Optimize tracking	Improves accuracy and comfort across users.	Medium

SR-5	The software shall follow GDPR by avoiding storage of personal data.	Legal compliance	Ensures privacy and data protection.	High
SR-6	The application shall be installable via desktop app or sideloaded APK.	Flexible deployment	Allows local and network installation options.	Medium
SR-7	The system shall operate on standalone VR headsets equipped with 6–12 GB of RAM and an XR2 or similar processor	Run on modern VR devices	Makes sure the application works smoothly on current VR hardware used in training environments.	High
SR-8	The system shall allow headset adjustment for glasses-wearing users.	Visual accessibility	Improves usability and comfort for all users.	High
SR-9	The application shall store scenario files in modular packages.	Modular content updates	Allows easy updates and version control.	Medium
SR-10	The application shall support hand tracking functionality via OpenXR-compatible APIs on supported headsets	Natural interaction	Supports a more intuitive and accessible user experience by allowing users to interact with the virtual environment using natural hand gestures	High
SR-11	The application shall be designed to minimize unnecessary user movement	Safe and comfortable training experience	Reduces the risk of motion sickness and allows trainers to provide a physically safe training space with minimal room requirements	High

7. User Requirements

This section outlines what the user need from the system to have a clear, comfortable, and effective training experience. The requirements are based on user feedback and aim to support different skill levels, learning styles, and real-world application. The user requirements were derived from qualitative analysis of user testing sessions and group interviews. Feedback was thematically analyzed to identify recurring user needs, such as intuitive controls, clear instructional guidance, and realistic training scenarios.

Req ID	Requirement	User Task	Rationale	Priority
UR-1	Users shall be able to complete the training without prior VR experience.	Accessibility	Broadens usability across skill levels.	High
UR-2	Users shall be able to receive guidance or hints during a scenario without having to leave or pause the training environment.	In-scenario support	Keeps immersion intact and reduces confusion by for instance adding a help button.	High
UR-3	Users shall receive feedback about correct or incorrect actions in real time.	Understand consequences	Builds procedural understanding and reflection.	High
UR-4	Users shall be able to make mistakes and learn from them without interrupting the VR experience.	Learn through trial and error	Supports learning by allowing users to explore, fail safely, and understand consequences.	High
UR-5	Users shall receive a performance summary after completing the training.	Progress awareness	Reinforces learning goals and improvement.	Medium
UR-6	Users shall feel confident in applying training knowledge to real situations.	Transfer of training	Supports goal of real-world preparedness.	High
UR-7	Users shall be able to complete a scenario in under 20 minutes.	Training efficiency	Fits into workplace schedules and reduces fatigue and cognitive overload.	Medium
UR-8	Users shall be able to pause training at any point.	Pacing control	Supports breaks and personal regulation.	Medium
UR-9	Users shall be able to adjust text size and interface scale.	Accessibility	Helps accommodate different visual needs.	Low
UR-10	Users shall be able to choose their preferred training language.	Understand content	Improves clarity and comfort for diverse users.	Low

UR-11	Users shall feel physically safe and have enough space in the real world to move comfortably during training.	Move with confidence	Reduces hesitation, fear of collisions, and physical discomfort, supporting better immersion and task performance.	High
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8. Data Requirements

This section explains how the system will manage training data, focusing on tracking progress, protecting user privacy, and meeting GDPR rules. It also includes features for trainers, like exporting feedback and analyzing performance.

Req ID	Requirement	User Task	Rationale	Priority
DR-1	The application shall log session performance metrics (e.g., time, accuracy, and completion).	Trainer insight	Enables post-training analysis and performance tracking.	High
DR-2	The application shall store anonymized user profiles.	Preserve user privacy	Ensures compliance with data protection principles while allowing usage tracking without collecting personal information.	High
DR-3	The application shall export logs in CSV and/or JSON formats.	Share and analyze training data	Facilitates compatibility with external tools.	Medium
DR-4	The application should log user interactions, including object use and task failure (e.g., missed PPE, skipped steps), in the final examination.	Assess procedure adherence and identify unsafe behaviors	Supports performance review and detailed evaluation of the most common mistakes.	High
DR-5	The application shall retain user logs only for as long as necessary for training and analysis purposes, with the retention period configurable by trainers.	Respect data retention limits	Supports compliance with data protection regulations while enabling trend analysis and reporting.	High
DR-6	The application shall track how many times each user repeats a scenario.	Engagement tracking	Helps identify persistence, improvement and helps to validate the system	Medium

9. Validation & Verification

Usability and user satisfaction should be assessed through the System Usability Scale (SUS) questionnaire, a benchmark that enables quantitative comparisons against established usability standards [5]. In addition, objective performance metrics could be gathered, including task completion time, error rates, and system responsiveness. These indicators provide data on how efficiently and accurately users complete training scenarios.

This approach is aligned with best practices described by de Giorgio et al., particularly the described experimental validation strategy. They recommend combining controlled experiments with test and control groups, pre- and post-training assessments, and continuous performance monitoring. Following this method ensures a robust evaluation, balancing objective performance data with user-reported experiences. Their findings highlight that relying only on subjective feedback can overlook critical usability or performance issues, while objective data alone may miss insights into user perception and learning effectiveness [6].

10. Traceability Matrix

The traceability matrix below links the high-level goals of the system to specific requirements and validation methods. Practically, this matrix answers the question: “How do we know that our system design and features actually support our goals?” Every individual requirement is not listed in the matrix, only the key examples presenting how critical user needs and training objectives are supported throughout the system.

Goal	Requirement Type	Req ID	Validation
Improve safety awareness through realistic simulations	Functional	FR-1, FR-6, FR-B1, FR-B2, FR-B3, FR-B5, FR-B7, FR-B8	User testing, expert review, scenario observation
Increase usability and user comfort	Non-Functional, User	NFR-1, NFR-3, NFR-5, UR-1, UR-8, UR-9, UR-11, FR-5, FR-9	SUS questionnaire, user testing with observation
Support learning from mistakes and reinforce retention	Functional, Data	FR-2, FR-3, FR-8, FR-10, DR-1, DR-4, DR-6	Log analysis, trainer feedback, performance summary
Ensure accessibility and inclusivity	System, User, Non-Functional	SR-2, SR-8, UR-9, UR-10, NFR-4, FR-11	Accessibility checklist, user feedback, multi-language testing
Prepare users for high-pressure and emergency situations	Functional	FR-6, FR-12, FR-B5, FR-B6	Simulated stress scenarios, observation

Support tracking, assessment and improvement of training outcomes	Data, Functional	DR-1, DR-3, DR-6, FR-3, FR-10, FR-8	Exported training logs, performance dashboards, final scenario scores
Maintain immersion and system performance	System, Non-Functional	NFR-1, NFR-6, NFR-7, NFR-10, SR-3, SR-7	Technical benchmarking (FPS, load time), in-VR observation
Ensure legal and ethical data handling	System, Data	SR-5, DR-2, DR-5	GDPR compliance review, anonymization check

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